

Enantioselective Synthesis of Spirocyclic Isoxazolones Using a Conia-Ene Type Reaction

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ABSTRACT: Stereoselective synthesis of spirocyclic compounds containing heterocyclic motifs represents a formidable challenge in enantioselective synthesis. Here, we present a cascade reaction between α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and isoxazolones under synergistic catalysis of a chiral secondary amine and a palladium(0) catalyst. This strategy allows access to chiral spiroisoxazolone derivatives with a large substrate scope tolerance and high levels of diastereoselectivity (dr up to 20:1) and enantioselectivity (up to 99% ee). Furthermore, the utility of this methodology is showcased by the transformation of chiral spiroisoxazolones into structurally attractive and enantiomerically enriched cyclopentene carboxylic acids with two stereogenic centers.

INTRODUCTION

Isoxazolines are versatile five-membered heterocyclic scaffolds with significant biological activities that also serve as important precursors in natural product synthesis to access amino acids¹ or hydroxy ketones.² Moreover, isoxazoline-based molecules have been explored for their anti-inflammatory,³ antibacterial,⁴ antifungal,⁵ and anticancer⁶ activities. Some compounds with the isoxazoline moiety, such as fluxametamide and isocycloseram, are used as agrochemicals for crop protection (Scheme 1A).⁷ Thus, the incorporation of an isoxazoline moiety as a bioactive framework into highly complex organic compounds can be attractive from the perspective of medicinal chemistry. It is noteworthy that spirocycles with increased rigidity are popular in medicinal chemistry today, resulting in various approved drugs and drug candidates. A combination of spatial rigidity caused by the presence of spirocyclic carbon centers and a heterocyclic moiety often leads to improvements in physicochemical properties and pharmacokinetic profiles.⁸ Therefore, enantioselective synthesis of spiro (hetero)-compounds represents one of the most challenging tasks in synthetic organic chemistry.⁹ Among other strategies, synergistic catalysis, which combines chiral organocatalysis with transition metal catalysis, has established itself as a suitable toolbox for synthesizing these molecules, which, in general, are challenging to prepare via a single catalytic mode.¹⁰ The most widely used strategy includes either tetrahydro-1*H*-oxepino ring expansion¹¹ or vinylcyclopropane ring contraction¹² of the corresponding heterocycle under transition metal catalyst activation, forming a corresponding zwitterionic species, which subsequently reacts with the iminium/enamine intermediate formed from enal under chiral secondary amine catalyst activation.

Despite the remarkable significance of the catalytic Conia-ene reaction in total synthesis under transition metal

catalysis,¹³ approaches employing an organocatalytic Conia-ene reaction in the synthesis of enantiopure spiro heterocycles are considerably less explored.¹⁴ Pioneering work employing synergistic catalysis of homogeneous Pd(II) complexes and secondary amines in the enantioselective synthesis of spirocyclopentenes with an oxindole moiety was introduced by Hong and Wang (Scheme 1B).^{14c} Soon thereafter, Córdova and Johnston reported a concept using a combined heterogeneous Pd(0)/chiral amine relay catalysis.^{13d} Besides oxindole, pyrazolone, another nitrogen-containing heterocycle, has been successfully used to construct chiral spiropyrazolones. In 2016, Enders's research group developed a sequential organocatalytic and silver catalytic approach,^{14c} and a few years later, our research group published the synthesis of spiropyrazolones using a synergistic Pd(0)/chiral secondary amine-promoted Conia-ene reaction (Scheme 1B).^{14b} Conversely, the enantioselective synthesis of spirocyclic compounds bearing an isoxazolone moiety has not yet been investigated under the catalytic Conia-ene reaction. With this regard and based on our continuous effort in the area of stereoselective synthesis,^{11a,c,e,12a,b,14b} we speculated that a propargyl-substituted isoxazolone derivative could under activation with a transition metal catalyst undergo a cyclization domino reaction with α,β -unsaturated aldehydes activated by a chiral secondary amine catalyst providing access to optically pure spiro isoxazolone derivatives (Scheme 1B).

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Scheme 1. (A) Bioactive Isoxazoline-Containing Compounds and (B) Synergistic Catalysis in the Construction of Spiro Heterocycles via the Conia-Ene Reaction
A) Representative Bioactive Isoxazoline-containing Compounds

This approach

B) Synergistic Construction of Spiro Heterocycles
Hong and Wang (2012)

Vesely (2019)

Table 1. Optimization of the Reaction Conditions between Isoxazolone 1a and Cinnamaldehyde 2a^a

entry	organocatalyst	metal catalyst	solvent	time (h)	conversion (%)	yield of the major/minor diastereoisomer (%)	dr ^b	ee of the major/minor diastereoisomer (%) ^c
1	I	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	MeCN	24	100	50/20	2.4:1	48/98
2	I	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	toluene	24	100	60/30	2:1	80/99
3	I	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	DCM	24	100	35/25	2.5:1	78/98
4	I	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	MTBE	24	100	40/18	1.3:1	68/99
5	I	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	24	100	63/30	2:1	88/99
6	II	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	72	100	24/12	2:1	56/92
7	III	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	120	100	45/39	1:1	64/98
8	IV	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	120	100	39/33	1:1	72/98
9	V	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	120	30	15/nd	2.5:1	18/–
10	VI	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	120	>10	nd/nd	–	–/–
11	VII	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	120	>10	nd/nd	–	–/–
12	I	Pd(PPh ₃) ₄	EtOAc	120	0	nd/nd	–	–/–
13	I	PdCl ₂	EtOAc	120	0	nd/nd	–	–/–
14	I	Pd(OAc) ₂	EtOAc	72	100	38/26	2:1	75/96
15	I	AuCl	EtOAc	120	0	nd/nd	–	–/–
16 ^d	I	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	120	90	43/25	2:1	80/99
17 ^e	I	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	120	0	nd/nd	–	–/–
18 ^f	I	Pd ₂ (dba) ₃	EtOAc	120	96	42/27	1.6:1	82/99

^aReaction conditions: catalyst I–VII (0.024 mmol, 20 mol %), enal 2a (0.12 mmol, 1.0 equiv), isoxazolone 1a (0.18 mmol, 1.5 equiv), and a solvent (1 mL) at rt. ^bDetermined by ¹H NMR. ^cDetermined by chiral HPLC. ^dWith 2 mol % Pd₂(dba)₃. ^eWith 2 mol % Pd₂(dba)₃ and 5 mol % I. ^fReaction carried out at 0 °C.

Scheme 2. Reaction Scope of α,β -Unsaturated Aldehyde Derivatives 2a–n^a

^aReaction conditions: catalyst I (0.024 mmol, 20 mol %), aldehyde 2a–h (0.12 mmol, 1.0 equiv), isoxazolone 1a (0.18 mmol, 1.5 equiv), and EtOAc (1 mL) at rt.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To probe the viability of this project, we commenced our investigation with the reaction between 3-phenyl-4-propargyl isoxazolone derivative 1a and cinnamaldehyde 2a in acetonitrile as a solvent under catalysis with a combination of tris(dibenzylideneacetone)dipalladium and a Hayashi–Jørgensen secondary amine catalyst (Table 1, entry 1). To our delight, the reaction provided the corresponding spiroisoxazolone derivative 3a as a separable mixture of two diastereoisomers (dr 2.4:1) in good yield. The major diastereoisomer was isolated in 50% yield (20% yield of the minor one) with an enantiomeric purity of 48% ee for the major diastereoisomer and 98% ee for the minor diastereoisomer. Prompted by this result, a small group of organic solvents have been studied in order to improve the

stereocontrol of the studied transformation (Table 1, entries 2–5). The obtained results clearly indicated that diastereocontrol of the reaction remained unchanged, but enantiocontrol was significantly improved in all cases, especially for the major diastereoisomer. Ethyl acetate, as the most effective solvent, provided 3a in a high yield of 63% for the major diastereoisomer and 30% for the minor diastereoisomer. Moreover, a high level of enantiomeric purity for both diastereoisomers (88% ee for the major diastereoisomer and 99% ee for the minor diastereoisomer, entry 5) was observed. Next, the effects of other transition metals and organocatalysts were studied (Table 1, entries 6–15). First, the role of a chiral organocatalyst was investigated, and apart from the Hayashi–Jørgensen secondary amine, other chiral secondary amines in combination with Pd₂(dba)₃ were tested. The obtained experimental data showed that the expected cyclization

Scheme 3. Reaction Scope of 3-Aliphatic-Substituted Isoxazolone Derivatives **1b** and **1c**^a

^aReaction conditions: catalyst I (0.024 mmol, 20 mol %), aldehyde **2** (0.12 mmol, 1.0 equiv), isoxazolone **1a-c** (0.18 mmol, 1.5 equiv), and EtOAc (1 mL) at rt.

also observed in the presence of other catalysts derived from diphenyl prolinols **II-V**.

However, the reaction carried out in the presence of other silyl-protected diphenyl prolinol catalysts showed a lower level of stereoselectivity (entries 6–8). The reaction catalyzed with non-protected diphenyl prolinol catalyst **V** provided spirocycle **3a** in a low yield and stereocontrol (entry 9). It is noteworthy that (*S*)-proline **VI** and imidazolidinone **VII** were found to be inefficient (entries 10 and 11, respectively). To probe the compatibility with model Hayashi–Jørgensen secondary amine catalyst **I**, a small set of achiral transition metal salts has been examined (Table 1, entries 12–15). We observed that not only Pd₂(dba)₃ but also Pd(OAc)₂ was effective together with a chiral Hayashi–Jørgensen secondary amine catalyst. However, when Pd(OAc)₂ was used, **3a** was isolated in moderate yield and enantiomeric purity for the major diastereoisomer (entry 14). Surprisingly, gold(I) chloride, known as an effective species in activating triple bonds in various transformations,¹⁵ was futile in our reaction. Next, the role of catalytic loading in the course of the reaction was tested (Table 1, entries 16 and 17). The obtained data clearly indicate that the decreased loading of both organocatalysts and transition metal catalysts has a negative effect on the course of the reaction. This resulted in the complete ceasing of the transformation when 2 mol % Pd₂(dba)₃ and 5 mol % organocatalyst **I** were used. We also demonstrated that a reaction carried out at 0 °C did not provide product **3a** with better stereoselectivity (entry 18).

With our optimized conditions in hand, the scope of the method was probed using different types of substrates. First, we examined the effect of substitution on the aromatic ring of cinnamaldehyde in the reaction with the isoxazolone derivative (**1a**) (Scheme 2). When *para*-brominated cinnamaldehyde (**2b**) was used with isoxazolone **1a**, spirocycle **3b** was delivered as a mixture of diastereoisomers in high yield (95%) and with a high level of enantiomeric purity for the major (88% ee) and minor (99% ee) diastereoisomers. On the other hand, the reaction proceeded with only a low diastereoselectivity (dr 2:1). An increased level of diastereocontrol of the spirocyclization reaction (dr 4.5:1) was observed using *p*-cyano-substituted cinnamaldehyde **2c**. Spiroisoxazolone derivative **3c** was isolated in 72% yield as an inseparable mixture of diastereoisomers with a high level of enantiomeric purity for

both diastereoisomers (87% and 99% ee for the major and minor enantiomers, respectively). Electron-donating methoxy and methyl groups in the *para* position of cinnamaldehyde were also well tolerated. Selectivities for both reactions were comparable (dr 2.3:1 to 2.2:1 and 87% and 96% ee to 85% and 96% ee for **3d** and **3e**, respectively), although the reactivities of both aldehydes were different. Whereas a full conversion of *p*-methoxy-substituted cinnamaldehyde (**2d**) was reached after 6 days, *p*-methyl-substituted cinnamaldehyde (**2e**) delivered the desired spiroisoxazolone **3e** after 3 days as a separable mixture of two diastereoisomers (48% and 25% for the major and minor enantiomers, respectively). Most importantly, a major diastereoisomer of **3e** was obtained as a crystalline material suitable for X-ray diffraction analysis, leading to the conclusion that the absolute configurations on the stereogenic centers were (*S*)-C3 and (*R*)-C4. Additionally, *m*-methyl-substituted cinnamaldehyde on the aromatic ring (**2f**) was successfully tested, affording spiroisoxazolone derivative **3f** as a separable mixture of two diastereoisomers with lower yields of 36% for the major diastereoisomer and 24% for the minor diastereoisomer, with high enantiomeric purities for both diastereoisomers (85% and 98% ee, respectively). Conversely, *o*-methyl-substituted cinnamaldehyde **1g** did not lead to the formation of spirocycle **3g** even after a prolonged reaction, probably due to steric hindrance of the methyl group in the *ortho* position on the aromatic ring. We also successfully tested an α,β -unsaturated aldehyde bearing a heteroaromatic furyl unit (**2h**). Product **3h** was delivered after 7 days as a separable mixture of diastereoisomers (42% and 32%) with a good level of enantiomeric purity for both diastereoisomers (78% and 87% ee). Again, the major diastereoisomer of **3h** was obtained as a single crystal suitable for X-ray analysis, confirming the same absolute configuration on both carbon stereogenic centers.

Next, we turned our attention to isoxazolones substituted with an R¹ alkyl group at position 3 (Scheme 3). When 3-methyl-4-propargyl isoxazolone (**1b**) was employed in the cyclization reaction with either aromatic or aliphatic α,β -unsaturated aldehydes (**2a**, **2g**, and **2k**), stereocontrol of the corresponding reactions was low. For example, the reaction between isoxazolone **1b** and aldehyde **2k** led to spirocycle **3q** with a low level of diastereoselectivity (dr 1.4:1) with

Scheme 4. Subsequent Transformation of Spiroisoxazolone Derivatives 3a and 3b

Scheme 5. Proposed Combined Iminium/Enamine and Pd-Catalyzed Michael/Carbocyclization between Isoxazolone 1 and Enal 2

enantioselectivities of 77% ee for the major diastereoisomer and 74% ee for the minor diastereoisomer. To improve diastereocontrol of the spirocyclization reaction, the sterically demanding 3-*tert*-butyl-4-propargyl isoxazolone (**1c**) was prepared and used in the cyclization reaction with cinnamic aldehyde **2a**. Increased steric hindrance resulted in a slow reaction course reaching full conversion after 7 days. On the other hand, excellent diastereoselectivity of the transformation (*dr* >20:1) led to the formation of product **3r** as a single diastereoisomer with a high level of enantiomeric purity (94% ee) in 49% yield. The absolute configuration of spirocycle **3r** was confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis, having the configuration on both carbon stereogenic centers (3*S* and 4*R*) identical to the previously determined configurations on the major diastereoisomers of **3f** and **3h**, respectively. To bring

the reactivity forward, cyclization reactions of isoxazolone **1c** with the sterically less demanding aliphatic *trans*-2-pentenal (**2i**) and *trans*-2-heptenal (**2k**) were carried out. To our delight, full conversion was reached in both cases after 24 h, and both reactions proceeded with a high level of diastereoselectivity (*dr* >20:1). Products **3s** and **3t** were isolated in good yields (79% for **3s** and 74% for **3t**) with a high level of enantiomeric excess (85% ee for **3s** and 90% ee for **3t**).

The robustness and versatility of the derivatives prepared as described above were demonstrated in the following transformations on model derivative **3a** and bromo derivative **3b** (Scheme 4). First, a scale-up experiment was carried out using 1 mmol of cinnamaldehyde (**2a**) and 1.5 mmol of isoxazolone **1a**. Spirocycle **3a** was delivered as a separable mixture of two diastereoisomers in 45% yield for the major diastereoisomer

and 27% yield for the minor diastereoisomer with a retained level of stereoselectivity (dr 2:1, 86% and 99% ee for the major and minor enantiomers, respectively) compared to the model reaction. Next, we showed that the aldehyde moiety in the major diastereoisomer of spiroisoxazolone derivative **3a** could be readily converted into the carboxylic group by the formation of derivative **4** in a high yield of 88% with an enantiomeric excess of 88% ee. We also demonstrated that the isoxazolone moiety in derivative **3b** can be cleaved in the presence of $\text{Mo}(\text{CO})_6$, forming compound **5** as a single diastereoisomer in 59% yield with an enantiomeric purity of 84% ee. We also showed that compound **5** can be obtained directly from starting isoxazolone derivative **1a** and enal **2b** using a one-pot synthetic procedure, including enantioselective spirocyclization/isoxazolone cleavage, in 41% yield with the same enantiomeric purity (84% ee). The aldehyde moiety of **5** was then successfully oxidized using Pinnick type oxidation, affording carboxylic acid **6** in 73% yield with retained enantiomeric excess (84% ee). The absolute configuration of **6** was then assigned on both stereogenic centers as 4*R*,5*R* after its co-crystallization with (*R*)-1-phenylethylamine.

Based on our previous report about the computational and mechanistic study of the Conia-ene reaction,^{14b} we proposed the reaction mechanism and key intermediates of the spirocyclization reaction of isoxazolones **1** with enals **2** to rationalize the stereochemistry of the cascade catalytic reaction (Scheme 5). We assume that the Pd(0) catalyst forms Pd(II) hydride species **III** with the enol form of isoxazolone **1** via oxidative addition.^{13b-j} Next, intermediate **III** undergoes conjugated addition with chiral iminium intermediate **II**, resulting in chiral enamine **IV**. After carbocyclization of **IV**, spiroheterocycle **3** is released from the catalytic cycle together with recycled chiral organocatalyst **I** and Pd(0).

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have developed a stereoselective approach to enantiomerically enriched spiroisoxazolone derivatives using easily accessible α,β -unsaturated aldehydes and propargyl-substituted isoxazolones. This cascade Conia-ene reaction effectively catalyzed by the synergy of chiral organocatalysis and tris(dibenzylideneacetone)dipalladium(0) exhibits high versatility and provides a wide array of spiroisoxazolones in good to high yields (36–97%) with high levels of diastereoselectivity (dr up to 20:1) and high enantioselectivities (ee up to 94% and 99% for the major and minor diastereoisomers, respectively). Furthermore, the synthetic utility was demonstrated on selected follow-up transformations, leading to enantiomerically enriched functionalized products.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

General Information. Chemicals and solvents were either purchased (puriss p.A.) from commercial suppliers or purified by standard techniques. For thin-layer chromatography (TLC), silica gel plates Merck 60 F₂₅₄ were used, and compounds were visualized by irradiation with UV light and/or by treatment with a solution of phosphomolybdic acid (25 g), $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10 g), concentrated H_2SO_4 (60 mL), and H_2O (940 mL) followed by heating. Column chromatography was performed using silica gel Merck 60 (particle size of 0.040–0.063 mm). ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and 2D NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker DPX600 NMR instrument. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million relative to residual solvent signals (CHCl_3 , 7.26 ppm for ¹H NMR; CDCl_3 , 77.1 ppm for ¹³C NMR). High-resolution mass spectra were recorded on an LCV Fleet

spectrometer using a Bruker Compact QTOF-MS instrument controlled by Compass 1.9 Control software to measure the ESI high-resolution mass spectra. The monoisotopic mass values were calculated using Data analysis software version 4.4. The analysis was conducted in positive ion mode over a scan range from 50 to 1000, and nitrogen was used as a nebulizer gas at a pressure of 4 psi and a flow of 3 L/min for the dry gas. The capillary voltage and temperature were set at 4500 V and 220 °C, respectively. Optical rotations were performed on an AU-Tomatica polarimeter; Autopol III. IR DRIFT spectra were recorded with a Nicolet AVATAR 370 FT-IR instrument in cm^{-1} instrument. HPLC analysis was performed on a LC20AD Shimadzu liquid chromatograph with an SPD-M20A diode array detector with a Daicel Chiralpak column.

Isoxazolones **1a** and **1b** are known compounds prepared according to the published methods.¹⁶ The spectral data of **1a** and **1b** are consistent with data published in the literature.^{16b,17}

3-(tert-Butyl)-4-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)isoxazol-5(4*H*)-one (1c). The title compound was prepared according to the same two-step procedure.¹⁶ The crude product was purified by silica gel flash chromatography with *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate (2:1) as the eluent to give **1c** as a pale red solid in 21% yield (0.9 g): ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.51 (t, *J* = 4.7 Hz, 1H), 2.91 (qdd, *J* = 17.4 Hz, *J'* = 4.7 Hz, *J''* = 2.6 Hz, 2H), 2.12 (t, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H), 1.32 (s, 9H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 177.4, 173.8, 77.2, 73.0, 45.4, 35.5, 28.2, 19.5; HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2\text{Na}$ [*M* + *Na*]⁺ 202.0838, found 202.0839.

Enal **2a** is a commercially available compound, and enals **2b–n** are known compounds, which were prepared and characterized according to the published methods.¹⁸

General Procedure for the Synthesis of Spiroisoxazolones 3a–t. To a screw cap septum vial containing EtOAc (1 mL) was added catalyst (*S*)-DPP-TMS **I** (0.024 mmol, 0.20 equiv), followed by the addition of (*E*)- α,β -unsaturated aldehydes **2a–t** (0.12 mmol, 1.0 equiv) and isoxazolone derivatives **1a–c** (0.18 mmol, 1.5 equiv). Then, $\text{Pd}_2(\text{dba})_3$ (0.006 mmol, 0.05 equiv) was added. After full conversion was reached (TLC monitoring), the solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the crude reaction mixture was purified through silica gel flash chromatography (*n*-Hex/EtOAc), affording the desired spirocyclic compounds **3a–t**.

(5*S*,6*R*)-8-Methyl-1-oxo-4,6-diphenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (3a) (major diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 2:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): yellow semisolid (20 mg, 50% yield); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.07 (s, 1H), 7.73–7.72 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.56 (m, 1H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 2H), 7.29–7.26 (m, 3H), 7.02–6.98 (m, 2H), 4.99 (s, 1H), 3.33–3.25 (m, 2H), 2.42 (s, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.7, 178.4, 167.1, 159.4, 136.2, 135.1, 132.3, 129.7 (2C), 128.7 (2C), 128.5, 128.2 (2C), 126.9, 126.6 (2C), 60.0, 56.7, 47.6, 14.8; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3563, 3405, 3315, 3025, 2851, 1670, 1347, 1269, 1242, 1180 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 88% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 250 nm; retention times, *t*_{major} = 11.1 min, *t*_{minor} = 13.1 min) at 25 °C; [α]_D²⁵ = –68.2° (*c* = 0.76, CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_3$ [*M* + *H*]⁺ 332.1281, found 332.1281.

(5*R*,6*R*)-8-Methyl-1-oxo-4,6-diphenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (3a) (minor diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 2:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): yellow semisolid (14 mg, 35% yield); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 7.34–7.32 (m, 1H), 7.20–7.17 (m, 2H), 7.14–7.12 (m, 2H), 7.01–6.97 (m, 1H), 6.94–6.92 (m, 2H), 6.68–6.67 (m, 2H), 5.00 (s, 1H), 3.43 (d, *J* = 19.2 Hz, 1H), 3.29 (d, *J* = 19.2 Hz, 1H), 2.45 (s, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.8, 182.4, 167.4, 158.3, 136.6, 134.7, 131.3, 128.5 (2C), 128.2 (2C), 128.0 (2C), 127.9, 126.9 (3C), 61.7, 57.2, 47.6, 14.9; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3405, 3028, 2932, 2914, 1799, 1428, 1350, 1242, 1177, 1102, 1075, 1048 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 99% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 70:30 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 243 nm; retention times, *t*_{minor} = 21.4 min, *t*_{major} = 24.8 min) at 25 °C; [α]_D²⁵ = –55.4° (*c* = 0.33, CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_3$ [*M* + *H*]⁺ 332.1281, found 332.1282.

(5*S*/5*R*,6*R*)-6-(4-Bromophenyl)-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3b**) (3:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude (dr 2:1) by silica gel chromatography (2.5:1 *n*-Hex/EA): yellow semisolid (47 mg, 95% yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 3:1); ^1H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 7.71–7.69 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.56 (m, 1H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 2H), 7.39 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 6.87 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 4.92 (s, 1H), 3.29 (m, 2H), 2.42 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.4, 178.3, 166.9, 160.1, 136.0, 134.2, 132.4, 131.8 (2C), 129.9 (2C), 129.8 (2C), 126.7, 126.6 (2C), 122.6, 59.3, 56.5, 47.6, 14.8; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 88% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 70:30 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 190$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 13.9$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 16.0$ min) at 25 °C; ^1H NMR minor diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.04 (s, 1H), 7.40–7.37 (m, 1H), 7.24–7.22 (m, 2H), 7.14–7.13 (m, 2H), 7.04 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 2H), 6.53 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 2H), 4.90 (s, 1H), 3.45 (d, $J = 19.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.28 (d, $J = 19.4$ Hz, 1H), 2.44 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.4, 182.1, 167.2, 159.2, 136.3, 133.9, 131.5, 131.2 (2C), 129.6 (2C), 128.6 (2C), 128.1, 126.8 (2C), 121.9, 60.9, 56.9, 47.6, 14.9; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 99% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 70:30 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 190$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 20.1$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 25.0$ min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (ATR) ν 2911, 2875, 2845, 1670, 1649, 1449, 1404, 1362, 1240, 1201, 1078 cm^{-1} ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -101.5^\circ$ ($c = 1.36$, CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrNO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 410.0386, found 410.0385.

4-((5*S*/5*R*,6*R*)-7-Formyl-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-dien-6-yl)benzotrionitrile (**3c**) (3.8:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude (dr 4.5:1) by silica gel chromatography (1.5:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (31 mg, 72% yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 3.8:1); ^1H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.10 (s, 1H), 7.71–7.69 (m, 2H), 7.61–7.58 (m, 1H), 7.56 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.54–7.51 (m, 2H), 7.10 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 4.98–4.96 (m, 1H), 3.34–3.30 (m, 2H), 2.46 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.2, 178.1, 166.7, 160.9, 140.6, 135.7, 132.6, 132.4 (2C), 129.9 (2C), 129.1 (2C), 126.6 (2C), 126.4, 118.6, 112.5, 59.4, 56.3, 47.9, 14.8; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 87% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 197$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 11.8$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 23.7$ min) at 25 °C; ^1H NMR minor diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.11 (s, 1H), 7.40–7.38 (m, 1H), 7.24 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.22–7.20 (m, 2H), 7.13–7.10 (m, 2H), 6.76 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 4.98–4.96 (m, 1H), 3.49 (d, $J = 19.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.34 (d, $J = 19.5$ Hz, 1H), 2.48 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.0, 181.8, 166.7, 160.1, 140.2, 136.0, 131.9, 131.7 (2C), 128.8 (2C), 128.8 (2C), 127.9, 126.7 (2C), 118.4, 111.7, 61.1, 56.6, 47.9, 14.9; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 99% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 197$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 15.2$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 17.0$ min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3061, 2962, 2911, 2226, 1793, 1667, 1503, 1422, 1365, 1290, 1213, 1174, 1105 cm^{-1} ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -144.1^\circ$ ($c = 0.47$, CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{NaO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 379.1053, found 379.1054.

(5*S*/5*R*,6*R*)-6-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3d**) (2.4:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude (dr 2.3:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (34 mg, 79% yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 2.4:1); ^1H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.04 (s, 1H), 7.73–7.71 (m, 2H), 7.58–7.55 (m, 1H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 2H), 6.93 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 6.79 (d, $J = 8.7$ Hz, 2H), 4.96–4.94 (m, 1H), 3.76 (s, 3H), 3.27–3.26 (m, 2H), 2.41 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.9, 178.6, 167.2, 159.6, 159.1, 136.3, 132.2, 129.7 (2C), 129.4 (2C), 127.0, 126.9, 126.6 (2C), 114.1 (2C), 59.6, 56.9, 55.3, 47.4, 14.8; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 87% (Lux-amylosa column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 254$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 14.6$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 26.4$ min) at 25 °C; ^1H NMR minor diastereoisomer

(600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.02 (s, 1H), 7.36–7.33 (m, 1H), 7.22–7.19 (m, 2H), 7.17–7.15 (m, 2H), 6.59 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.45 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 4.96–4.94 (m, 1H), 3.64 (s, 3H), 3.42 (d, $J = 19.7$ Hz, 1H), 3.29 (d, $J = 19.7$ Hz, 1H), 2.43 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.9, 182.4, 167.5, 159.1, 158.1, 136.7, 131.2, 129.1 (2C), 128.5 (2C), 127.2, 126.9 (2C), 126.9, 113.6 (2C), 61.2, 57.4, 55.3, 47.3, 14.9; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 96% (Lux-amylosa column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 254$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 18.8$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 20.9$ min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3007, 2956, 2935, 2839, 1667, 1607, 1467, 1305, 1293, 1207, 1177 cm^{-1} ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -143.5^\circ$ ($c = 0.58$, CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_4$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 362.1387, found 362.1388.

(5*S*/5*R*,6*R*)-8-Methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-6-(*p*-tolyl)-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3e**) (major diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 2.2:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (19 mg, 48% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 7.72 (dd, $J = 7.2$ Hz, $J' = 1.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.61–7.54 (m, 1H), 7.50 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.07 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 6.89 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 4.96 (q, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.27 (dt, $J = 3.4$ Hz, $J' = 1.7$ Hz, 2H), 2.41 (s, 3H), 2.29 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.9, 178.5, 167.2, 159.2, 138.2, 136.3, 132.2 (2C), 132.0, 129.7 (2C), 129.4 (2C), 128.1 (2C), 126.7 (2C), 59.8, 56.8, 47.5, 21.3, 14.8; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3316, 3018, 2949, 2923, 2901, 1790, 1668, 1444, 1236, 1174, 885 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 85% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 254$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 14.0$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 16.6$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -95.2^\circ$ ($c = 0.53$, CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{NNaO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 368.1257, found 368.1255.

(5*S*/5*R*,6*R*)-8-Methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-6-(*p*-tolyl)-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3e**) (minor diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 2.2:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (10 mg, 25% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.02 (s, 1H), 7.34 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 1H), 7.19 (t, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.14 (dd, $J = 8.0$ Hz, $J' = 1.6$ Hz, 2H), 6.73 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 6.56 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 4.96 (d, $J = 2.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.41 (d, $J = 19.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.26 (d, $J = 19.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.43 (s, 3H), 2.13 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.9, 182.4, 167.5, 158.1, 137.6, 136.6, 131.7, 131.2, 128.8 (2C), 128.4 (2C), 128.3, 127.9 (2C), 127.0 (2C), 61.5, 57.4, 47.4, 21.1, 14.9; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3309, 3053, 2920, 2854, 1786, 1662, 1637, 1446, 1174, 773 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee 96% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 254$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 14.0$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 25.6$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -88.7^\circ$ ($c = 0.31$, CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{NNaO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 368.1257, found 368.1255.

(5*S*,6*R*)-8-Methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-6-(*m*-tolyl)-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3f**) (major diastereoisomer). The crude product (reaction time of 3 days, dr 1.8:1) was purified by silica gel flash chromatography with a 3:1 *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate eluent to give **3f** as a pale yellow oil in 36% yield (16 mg): ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.10 (s, 1H), 7.71–7.69 (m, 2H), 7.61–7.58 (m, 1H), 7.56 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.54–7.51 (m, 2H), 7.10 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 4.98–4.96 (m, 1H), 3.34–3.30 (m, 2H), 2.46 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.2, 178.1, 166.7, 160.9, 140.6, 135.7, 132.6, 132.4 (2C), 129.9 (2C), 129.1 (2C), 126.6 (2C), 126.4, 118.6, 112.5, 59.4, 56.3, 47.9, 14.8; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3012, 2922, 2868, 1797, 1662, 1442, 1365, 1264, 1078 cm^{-1} ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -61.9^\circ$ ($c = 0.42$, CHCl_3); HPLC analysis ee 85% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 0.5 mL/min, $\lambda = 254$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 18.2$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 20.9$ min) at 25 °C; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 346.1438, found 346.1437.

(5*R*,6*R*)-8-Methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-6-(*m*-tolyl)-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3f**) (minor diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 1.8:1) by silica gel chromatography (3:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (10 mg, 24% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.11 (s, 1H), 7.40–7.38 (m, 1H), 7.24 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.22–7.20 (m, 2H), 7.13–7.10 (m, 2H), 6.76 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 4.98–4.96 (m, 1H), 3.49 (d, $J = 19.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.34 (d, $J = 19.5$

H_z, 1H), 2.48 (s, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 186.0, 181.8, 166.7, 160.1, 140.2, 136.0, 131.9, 131.7 (2C), 128.8 (2C), 128.8 (2C), 127.9, 126.7 (2C), 118.4, 111.7, 61.1, 56.6, 47.9, 14.9; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3288, 3024, 2918, 2850, 1784, 1672, 1433, 1182, 1099 cm⁻¹; HPLC analysis ee 98% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 197 nm; retention times, *t*_{major} = 34.9 min, *t*_{minor} = 31.0 min) at 25 °C; [α]_D²⁵ = -94.5° (c = 0.28, CHCl₃); HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for C₂₂H₁₉NO₃ [M + H]⁺ 346.1438, found 346.1436.

(5*S*,6*R*)-6-(Furan-2-yl)-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3h**) (major diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 1.2:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (16 mg, 42% yield); mp 155–157 °C (*iso*-propanol); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 7.69–7.59 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.51 (m, 1H), 7.48 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 2H), 7.32 (d, *J* = 1.8 Hz, 1H), 6.31 (dd, *J* = 3.3 Hz, *J'* = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 6.11 (d, *J* = 3.2 Hz, 1H), 5.13–4.95 (m, 1H), 3.47–3.29 (m, 1H), 3.19 (dt, *J* = 19.5 Hz, *J'* = 1.3 Hz, 1H), 2.38 (s, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 186.3, 178.2, 167.2, 159.2, 148.7, 142.8, 134.6, 132.2, 129.7 (2C), 126.8, 126.6 (2C), 110.9, 109.1, 55.2, 53.0, 47.7, 14.8; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3159, 2925, 2854, 1797, 1664, 1552, 1498, 1234, 1014, 891 cm⁻¹; HPLC analysis ee 78% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 200 nm; retention times, *t*_{major} = 17.5 min, *t*_{minor} = 21.5 min) at 25 °C; [α]_D²⁵ = -69.4° (c = 0.56, CHCl₃); HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for C₁₉H₁₅NNaO₄ [M + Na]⁺ 344.0893, found 344.0891.

(5*R*,6*R*)-6-(furan-2-yl)-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3h**) (minor diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 1.2:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (12 mg, 32% yield); ¹H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.04 (s, 1H), 7.44–7.34 (m, 3H), 7.28 (m, 2H), 6.85 (d, *J* = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 5.96 (dd, *J* = 3.4 Hz, *J'* = 1.9 Hz, 1H), 5.86 (d, *J* = 3.3 Hz, 1H), 4.98 (d, *J* = 2.0 Hz, 1H), 3.40 (d, *J* = 19.3 Hz, 1H), 3.22 (d, *J* = 19.4 Hz, 1H), 2.39 (s, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 186.2, 181.7, 166.9, 158.1, 148.5, 141.8, 135.0, 131.4, 128.5 (2C), 127.3, 127.1 (2C), 110.6, 109.2, 56.0, 54.6, 47.6, 14.8; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3294, 3120, 2924, 2852, 1784, 1668, 1442, 1176, 883 cm⁻¹; HPLC analysis ee 87% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 200 nm; retention times, *t*_{minor} = 16.7 min, *t*_{major} = 31.0 min) at 25 °C; [α]_D²⁵ = -76.1° (c = 0.36, CHCl₃); HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for C₁₉H₁₅NNaO₄ [M + Na]⁺ 344.0893, found 344.0891.

(5*S*/*5R*,6*R*)-6,8-Dimethyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3i**) (2.1:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude (dr 2.2:1) by silica gel chromatography (3:1 *n*-Hex/EA): yellow semisolid (31 mg, 96% yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 2.1:1); ¹H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 7.61–7.60 (m, 2H), 7.53–7.49 (m, 1H), 7.45–7.42 (m, 2H), 3.80–3.76 (m, 1H), 3.17–3.16 (m, 2H), 2.26 (s, 3H), 1.34 (d, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 187.2, 179.5, 167.6, 157.5, 138.4, 132.1, 129.5 (2C), 126.9, 126.6 (2C), 55.1, 48.4, 47.4, 14.7, 14.3; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 70% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 190 nm; retention times, *t*_{minor} = 26.2 min, *t*_{major} = 29.6 min) at 25 °C; ¹H NMR minor diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.09 (s, 1H), 7.67–7.65 (m, 2H), 7.53–7.49 (m, 1H), 7.45–7.42 (m, 2H), 3.84–3.81 (m, 1H), 3.18 (d, *J* = 19.4 Hz, 1H), 3.05 (d, *J* = 19.4 Hz, 1H), 2.27 (s, 3H), 1.21 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 187.1, 182.6, 167.7, 157.6, 138.6, 132.0, 129.3 (2C), 128.4, 127.2 (2C), 55.8, 52.1, 47.3, 14.5, 14.3; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 90% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 190 nm; retention times, *t*_{major} = 34.3 min, *t*_{minor} = 52.5 min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3064, 2917, 2765, 1784, 1643, 1419, 1350, 1242, 1183 cm⁻¹; [α]_D²⁵ = -13.8° (c = 1.30 in CHCl₃); HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for C₁₆H₁₅O₃NNa [M + Na]⁺ 292.0944, found 292.0944.

(5*S*/*5R*,6*R*)-6-Ethyl-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3j**) (2.1:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude (dr 1.9:1) by silica gel chromatography (3:1 *n*-Hex/EA): yellow semisolid (32 mg, 94%

yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 2.1:1); ¹H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.04 (s, 1H), 7.60–7.58 (m, 2H), 7.53–7.50 (m, 1H), 7.45–7.42 (m, 2H), 3.62 (d, *J* = 11.1 Hz, 1H), 3.22–3.13 (m, 2H), 2.25 (s, 3H), 2.19–2.12 (m, 1H), 1.81–1.73 (m, 1H), 0.81 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 187.5, 180.1, 168.8, 157.6, 138.3, 132.1, 129.5 (2C), 126.7, 126.6 (2C), 55.8, 52.9, 49.1, 21.9, 14.3, 12.2; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 76% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 0.5 mL/min, λ = 200 nm; retention times, *t*_{major} = 19.1 min, *t*_{minor} = 22.1 min) at 25 °C; ¹H NMR minor diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.07 (s, 1H), 7.69–7.68 (m, 2H), 7.53–7.50 (m, 1H), 7.45–7.42 (m, 2H), 3.67 (d, *J* = 8.9 Hz, 1H), 3.13 (d, *J* = 19.5 Hz, 1H), 3.04 (d, *J* = 19.5 Hz, 1H), 2.34–2.27 (m, 1H), 2.25 (s, 3H), 1.28–1.20 (m, 1H), 0.78 (t, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 187.5, 183.1, 168.0, 157.8, 138.3, 132.0, 129.3 (2C), 128.2, 127.1 (2C), 59.5, 54.6, 48.8, 21.6, 14.3, 12.4; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 90% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 0.5 mL/min, λ = 200 nm; retention times, *t*_{minor} = 20.3 min, *t*_{major} = 28.0 min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3055, 2996, 2760, 1780, 1646, 1391, 1246, 1218, 1180, 1115 cm⁻¹; [α]_D²⁵ = -20.2° (c = 1.61 in CHCl₃); HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for C₁₇H₁₇O₃NNa [M + Na]⁺ 306.1101, found 306.1100.

(5*S*/*5R*,6*R*)-8-Methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-6-propyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3k**) (2.1:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude (dr 1.7:1) by silica gel chromatography (4:1 *n*-Hex/EA): yellow oil (35 mg, 97% yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 2.1:1); ¹H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.04 (s, 1H), 7.59–7.58 (m, 2H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 1H), 7.44–7.42 (m, 2H), 3.62 (d, *J* = 11.1 Hz, 1H), 3.22–3.13 (m, 2H), 2.24 (s, 3H), 2.19–2.12 (m, 1H), 1.81–1.73 (m, 1H), 1.22–1.11 (m, 2H), 0.81 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 187.3, 180.0, 168.8, 157.2, 138.5, 132.1, 129.5 (2C), 126.9, 126.6 (2C), 53.8, 53.2, 49.2, 30.8, 21.0, 14.2, 14.0; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 74% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1 mL/min, λ = 190 nm; retention times, *t*_{major} = 13.1 min, *t*_{minor} = 16.1 min) at 25 °C; ¹H NMR minor diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.06 (s, 1H), 7.68–7.66 (m, 2H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 1H), 7.44–7.42 (m, 2H), 3.74 (d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 3.15 (d, *J* = 19.3 Hz, 1H), 3.04 (d, *J* = 19.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H), 2.19–2.13 (m, 2H), 1.22–1.11 (m, 2H), 0.72 (t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 187.3, 182.9, 168.2, 157.3, 138.4, 132.0, 129.3 (2C), 128.4, 127.2 (2C), 57.2, 54.9, 48.8, 30.6, 21.1, 14.0, 13.9; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 94% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1 mL/min, λ = 190 nm; retention times, *t*_{major} = 18.7 min, *t*_{minor} = 23.1 min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3064, 2959, 2872, 1799, 1673, 1446, 1344, 1296, 1210, 1108 cm⁻¹; [α]_D²⁵ = -23.4° (c = 1.56 in CHCl₃); HRMS (ESI) *m/z* calcd for C₁₈H₁₉O₃NNa [M + Na]⁺ 320.1257, found 320.1256.

(5*S*/*5R*,6*R*)-6-Butyl-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3l**) (2.2:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude (dr 1.7:1) by silica gel chromatography (3:1 *n*-Hex/EA): yellow semisolid (34 mg, 92% yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 2.2:1); ¹H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.03 (s, 1H), 7.60–7.58 (m, 2H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 1H), 7.45–7.41 (m, 2H), 3.67 (d, *J* = 11.0 Hz, 1H), 3.21–3.12 (m, 2H), 2.24 (s, 3H), 2.08–2.02 (m, 1H), 1.80–1.73 (m, 1H), 1.26–1.15 (m, 3H), 1.14–1.08 (m, 1H), 0.82 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 3H); ¹³C{¹H} NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 187.3, 180.1, 168.8, 157.1, 138.5, 132.1, 129.5 (2C), 126.9, 126.6 (2C), 54.0, 53.2, 49.2, 29.7, 28.4, 22.6, 14.2, 13.8; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 80% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 200 nm; retention times, *t*_{minor} = 11.7 min, *t*_{major} = 13.9 min) at 25 °C; ¹H NMR minor diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 10.06 (s, 1H), 7.69–7.66 (m, 2H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 1H), 7.45–7.41 (m, 2H), 3.72 (d, *J* = 11.1 Hz, 1H), 3.16 (d, *J* = 19.3 Hz, 1H), 3.05 (d, *J* = 19.3 Hz, 1H), 2.24 (s, 3H), 2.21–2.15 (m, 1H), 1.14–1.08 (m, 3H), 1.08–1.02 (m,

2H), 0.72 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 187.3, 182.9, 168.1, 157.2, 138.5, 132.0, 129.3 (2C), 128.4, 127.2 (2C), 57.4, 54.9, 48.9, 29.9, 28.1, 22.4, 13.8, 13.7; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 95% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 200$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 16.4$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 20.6$ min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (ATR) ν 2959, 2935, 2854, 1670, 1640, 1425, 1347, 1254, 1180 cm^{-1} ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -30.1^\circ$ ($c = 1.15$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_3\text{NNa}$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 334.1414, found 334.1412.

(5S/5R,6R)-6-(But-3-en-1-yl)-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3m**) (2.8:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude (dr 2.7:1) by silica gel chromatography (3:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (27 mg, 74% yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 2.8:1); ^1H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.03 (s, 1H), 7.58–7.56 (m, 2H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 1H), 7.45–7.41 (m, 2H), 5.67–5.55 (m, 1H), 4.94–4.89 (m, 1H), 4.85 (d, $J = 10.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.73 (d, $J = 11.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.23–3.16 (m, 2H), 2.25 (s, 3H), 2.20–2.13 (m, 1H), 2.05–1.98 (m, 1H), 1.93–1.81 (m, 2H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 187.2, 180.1, 168.6, 157.4, 138.4, 136.9, 132.1, 129.5 (2C), 126.9, 126.6 (2C), 116.3, 56.2, 52.7, 49.3, 31.7, 27.8, 14.3; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 74% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 190$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 13.5$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 16.8$ min) at 25 °C; ^1H NMR minor diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.07 (s, 1H), 7.69–7.67 (m, 2H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 1H), 7.45–7.41 (m, 2H), 5.67–5.55 (m, 1H), 4.94–4.89 (m, 2H), 3.77 (d, $J = 11.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.14 (d, $J = 19.3$ Hz, 1H), 3.06 (d, $J = 19.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.36–2.28 (m, 1H), 2.25 (s, 3H), 1.93–1.81 (m, 2H), 1.37–1.30 (m, 1H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 187.2, 182.7, 168.0, 157.5, 138.4, 136.7, 132.1, 129.4 (2C), 128.3, 127.2 (2C), 116.3, 54.7, 53.0, 48.9, 31.8, 27.8, 14.3; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 91% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 190$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 20.4$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 23.9$ min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3076, 2947, 2845, 2762, 1673, 1443, 1377, 1341, 1287, 1198, 1180 cm^{-1} ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -20.7^\circ$ ($c = 0.92$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 309.1365, found 309.1364.

Ethyl (5S,6R)-7-Formyl-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-6-carboxylate (**3n**) (major diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 2.5:1) by silica gel chromatography (4:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (15 mg, 38% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.07 (s, 1H), 7.61–7.50 (m, 2H), 7.48–7.42 (m, 1H), 4.43 (s, 1H), 4.25–4.06 (m, 2H), 3.33 (d, $J = 19.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.18 (d, $J = 19.5$ Hz, 1H), 2.32 (s, 3H), 1.34–1.13 (m, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.4, 179.3, 167.7, 167.1, 158.1, 134.2, 132.4, 129.7 (2C), 126.4 (2C), 62.3, 57.7, 52.5, 49.3, 14.5, 13.8; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3066, 2960, 2850, 1790, 1743, 1668, 1444, 1180 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee 80% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 70:30 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 254$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 9.6$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 19.7$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -45.5^\circ$ ($c = 0.55$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_5$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 327.1107, found 327.1108.

Ethyl (5R,6R)-7-Formyl-8-methyl-1-oxo-4-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-6-carboxylate (**3n**) (minor diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 2.5:1) by silica gel chromatography (4:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (9 mg, 23% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.05 (s, 1H), 7.62 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.49 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, 1H), 7.41 (t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, 2H), 4.49 (s, 1H), 3.84–3.67 (m, 1H), 3.64–3.52 (m, 1H), 3.25 (d, $J = 19.5$ Hz, 1H), 3.20 (d, $J = 19.4$ Hz, 1H), 2.32 (s, 3H), 0.95 (td, $J = 7.2$, 2.1 Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.1, 181.5, 167.6, 166.3, 157.1, 134.5, 132.3, 129.1 (2C), 127.0 (2C), 126.5, 62.0, 59.1, 52.4, 48.8, 14.5, 13.6; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3060, 2985, 2854, 1792, 1174, 1670, 1188 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee 76% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 70:30 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 254$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 12.9$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 15.4$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -36.4^\circ$ ($c = 0.22$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_5$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 327.1107, found 327.1106.

(5S,6R)-4,8-Dimethyl-1-oxo-6-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3o**) (major diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 1.1:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow solid (15 mg, 45% yield); mp 157.8 °C (*iso*-propanol); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.03 (s, 1H), 7.33–7.28 (m, 3H), 7.03–7.00 (m, 2H), 4.73 (s, 1H), 2.98 (d, $J = 18.9$ Hz, 1H), 2.90 (d, $J = 18.9$ Hz, 1H), 2.39 (s, 3H), 1.24 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.4, 181.1, 167.5, 158.2, 136.4, 135.8, 129.2 (2C), 128.6, 127.8 (2C), 59.4, 56.7, 44.9, 14.7, 13.0; FT-IR (KBr) ν 2950, 2854, 1784, 1658, 1580, 1455, 1380, 1305, 1242, 1168 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee 88% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 90:10 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 233$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 15.7$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 17.8$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -165.3^\circ$ ($c = 0.38$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 270.1125, found 270.1129.

(5R,6R)-4,8-Dimethyl-1-oxo-6-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3o**) (minor diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 1.1:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow solid (15 mg, 45% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.00 (s, 1H), 7.31–7.25 (m, 3H), 7.01–6.99 (m, 2H), 4.48 (s, 1H), 3.18 (d, $J = 19.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.78 (d, $J = 19.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.38 (s, 3H), 2.13 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.3, 177.3, 168.1, 158.6, 136.7, 134.7, 128.8 (2C), 128.6, 128.1 (2C), 57.9, 56.9, 45.4, 14.6, 12.0; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3061, 3013, 1799, 1664, 1494, 1392, 1296, 1177 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 80% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 190$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 8.4$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 9.3$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -9.4^\circ$ ($c = 0.32$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 270.1125, found 270.1123.

(5S,6R)-4,8-Dimethyl-1-oxo-6-(*o*-tolyl)-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3p**) (major diastereoisomer). Purification of crude oil (dr 1.9:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (13 mg, 37% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.00 (s, 1H), 7.22–7.16 (m, 2H), 7.12–7.08 (m, 1H), 6.89–6.87 (m, 1H), 4.95 (s, 1H), 3.06 (d, $J = 19.1$ Hz, 1H), 2.83 (d, $J = 19.1$ Hz, 1H), 2.40 (s, 3H), 2.26 (s, 3H), 1.14 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.1, 181.5, 167.9, 157.6, 137.5, 136.8, 134.5, 131.7, 128.4, 126.9, 126.3, 55.2, 55.0, 45.4, 19.8, 14.6, 12.9; FT-IR (KBr) ν 2950, 2854, 1784, 1604, 1580, 1455, 1380, 1305, 1242, 1168 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 82% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 95:5 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 190$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 20.3$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 22.0$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -170.1^\circ$ ($c = 0.435$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 284.1281, found 284.1289.

(5R,6R)-4,8-Dimethyl-1-oxo-6-(*o*-tolyl)-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3p**) (minor diastereoisomer). Purification of crude (dr 1.9:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (8 mg, 24% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.99 (s, 1H), 7.18–7.10 (m, 3H), 6.89–6.87 (m, 1H), 4.73 (s, 1H), 3.25 (d, $J = 19.2$ Hz, 1H), 2.71 (d, $J = 19.2$ Hz, 1H), 2.40 (s, 3H), 2.24 (s, 3H), 2.11 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.1, 177.0, 168.8, 158.0, 137.8, 136.0, 132.9, 131.2, 128.2, 127.6, 126.1, 55.2, 53.1, 46.1, 19.7, 14.5, 11.9; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3061, 2926, 1799, 1640, 1434, 1341, 1296, 1216 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 69% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 97:3 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 223$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 26.7$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 31.5$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -24.6^\circ$ ($c = 0.29$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 284.1281, found 284.1285.

(5S/5R,6R)-4,8-Dimethyl-1-oxo-6-propyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3q**) (1.4:1 mixture of diastereoisomers). Purification of crude oil (dr 1.3:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale brown semisolid (27 mg, 96% yield) as a mixture of diastereoisomers (dr 1.4:1); ^1H NMR major diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.00 (s, 1H), 3.56–3.52 (m, 1H), 2.65 (d, $J = 19.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.60 (d, $J = 19.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.30–2.24 (m, 1H), 2.20 (s, 3H), 2.05 (s, 3H), 1.27–1.11 (m, 3H), 0.88 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR major diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 187.3, 181.2, 168.0, 156.9, 137.5, 56.5, 54.4, 46.3, 30.7,

20.9, 14.4, 14.1, 14.0; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 77% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 95:5 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 202$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 21.1$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 23.5$ min) at 25 °C; ^1H NMR minor diastereoisomer (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.97 (s, 1H), 3.23–3.20 (m, 1H), 3.11 (d, $J = 19.0$ Hz, 1H), 3.00 (d, $J = 19.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.20 (s, 3H), 1.95 (s, 3H), 1.74–1.70 (m, 2H), 1.27–1.11 (m, 2H), 0.85 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR minor diastereoisomer (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.8, 179.1, 169.2, 156.6, 138.7, 54.0, 51.8, 46.5, 30.8, 21.4, 14.1, 13.9, 11.7; HPLC analysis ee (minor diastereoisomer) 74% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 95:5 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 202$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 18.2$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 19.4$ min) at 25 °C; FT-IR (KBr) ν 2962, 2872, 1787, 1673, 1443, 1383, 1338, 1266, 1210, 1117 cm^{-1} ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -18.4^\circ$ ($c = 0.95$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 236.1281, found 236.1286.

(5*R*,6*R*)-4-(*tert*-Butyl)-8-methyl-1-oxo-6-phenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3r**). Purification of crude (dr 20:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow solid (18 mg, 49% yield); mp 87–89 °C (*iso*-propanol); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 10.01 (s, 1H), 7.31–7.23 (m, 3H), 7.02–6.95 (m, 2H), 4.82 (d, $J = 1.9$ Hz, 1H), 3.18 (ddd, $J = 19.3$ Hz, $J' = 2.3$ Hz, $J'' = 1.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.11 (dt, $J = 19.3$ Hz, $J' = 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.36 (s, 1H), 1.40 (s, 9H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 186.5, 178.4, 175.6, 159.6, 136.5, 135.1, 128.6, 128.5, 128.3, 58.5, 58.1, 46.3, 36.5, 29.7, 14.6; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3325, 2966, 2854, 1784, 1670, 1454, 1178, 1092 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee (major diastereoisomer) 94% (Daicel Chiralpak IC column, 80:20 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 210$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 13.8$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 19.0$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = 4.4^\circ$ ($c = 0.56$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{H}]^+$ 312.1594, found 312.1593.

(5*R*,6*R*)-4-(*tert*-Butyl)-6-ethyl-8-methyl-1-oxo-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3s**). Purification of crude (dr 20:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (21 mg, 79% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.98 (s, 1H), 3.56–3.46 (m, 1H), 3.06 (ddd, $J = 19.4$ Hz, $J' = 2.3$ Hz, $J'' = 1.3$ Hz, 1H), 2.97 (dt, $J = 19.3$ Hz, $J' = 1.1$ Hz, 1H), 2.19 (d, $J = 1.5$ Hz, 3H), 1.97 (dq, $J = 14.4$ Hz, $J' = 7.7$ Hz, $J'' = 3.3$ Hz, 1H), 1.73 (ddd, $J = 14.3$ Hz, $J' = 10.6$ Hz, $J'' = 7.1$ Hz, 1H), 1.29 (s, 9H), 0.83 (t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 187.2, 180.1, 176.9, 157.6, 138.8, 54.9, 54.0, 48.1, 36.5, 29.7 (3C), 22.0, 14.2, 12.6; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3296, 2968, 2937, 2879, 1776, 1655, 1574, 1462, 1178, 1028, 883 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee 85% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 95:5 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 240$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 11.8$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 13.0$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = 60.9^\circ$ ($c = 0.64$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{21}\text{NNaO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 286.1414, found 286.1413.

(5*R*,6*R*)-4-(*tert*-Butyl)-6-butyl-8-methyl-1-oxo-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carbaldehyde (**3t**). Purification of crude (dr 20:1) by silica gel chromatography (2:1 *n*-Hex/EA): pale yellow semisolid (26 mg, 74% yield); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.97 (s, 1H), 3.55 (d, $J = 10.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.07 (d, $J = 20.0$ Hz, 1H), 2.96 (d, $J = 19.4$ Hz, 1H), 2.19 (s, 3H), 1.85 (tdd, $J = 11.2$ Hz, $J' = 5.8$ Hz, $J'' = 3.0$ Hz, 1H), 1.70 (dtd, $J = 14.5$ Hz, $J' = 10.5$ Hz, $J'' = 4.3$ Hz, 1H), 1.28 (s, 9H), 1.26–1.23 (m, 2H), 1.22–1.13 (m, 1H), 1.11–1.03 (m, 1H), 0.84 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 187.1, 180.1, 176.8, 157.4, 139.0, 54.9, 52.4, 48.1, 36.5, 30.3, 29.7, 28.5, 22.7, 14.1, 13.9; FT-IR (ATR) ν 3060, 2958, 2931, 2871, 1780, 1668, 1178, 881 cm^{-1} ; HPLC analysis ee 90% (Daicel Chiralpak IB column, 98:2 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 240$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 13.1$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 14.3$ min) at 25 °C; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = 40.6^\circ$ ($c = 0.88$ in CHCl_3); HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{23}\text{NNaO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 314.1727, found 314.1727.

Preparation of Acid Derivative 4. (5*S*,6*R*)-8-Methyl-1-oxo-4,6-diphenyl-2-oxa-3-azaspiro[4.4]nona-3,7-diene-7-carboxylic Acid. To compound **3a** (64.0 mg, 0.19 mmol) in acetone (7 mL) and DMSO (2 mL) was dropwise added a mixture of NaClO_2 (86.0 mg, 0.95 mmol) and KH_2PO_4 (129.0 mg, 0.95 mmol) dissolved in H_2O (6 mL). After the mixture was stirred for 3 h, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, and the residue was extracted with ethyl acetate (4 \times 25 mL). The combined organic layer was washed

with H_2O (1 \times 50 mL) and a brine solution (1 \times 50 mL). The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and the solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The crude product was purified by silica gel flash chromatography in a 20:1 DCM/MeOH eluent to give **4** as a white solid (58 mg, 88% yield): mp 195.7 °C (ethyl acetate/*n*-heptane); ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.76–7.73 (m, 2H), 7.58–7.55 (m, 1H), 7.52–7.49 (m, 2H), 7.30–7.26 (m, 3H), 7.05–7.02 (m, 2H), 4.95 (s, 1H), 3.27 (d, $J = 19.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.19 (d, $J = 19.2$ Hz, 1H), 2.34 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 178.5, 168.9, 167.3, 156.9, 136.3, 132.2, 129.71 (2C), 128.75 (2C), 128.5, 127.9 (2C), 127.1, 126.9, 126.6 (2C), 61.3, 56.3, 47.8, 16.6; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3034, 2923, 2660, 1793, 1649, 1428, 1362, 1266, 1048 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NNaO}_4$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 370.1050, found 370.1046; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -92.3^\circ$ ($c = 1.92^\circ$ in MeOH); HPLC analysis ee 88% (Daicel Chiralpak IG column, 70:30 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 198$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{major}} = 5.9$ min, $t_{\text{minor}} = 9.0$ min) at 25 °C.

Preparation of Derivative 5. (4*R*,5*R*)-4-Benzoyl-5-(4-bromophenyl)-2-methylcyclopent-1-ene-1-carbaldehyde. A solution of $\text{Mo}(\text{CO})_6$ (63.4 mg, 0.24 mmol) in CH_3CN (3 mL) was refluxed using an oil bath for 3 h. Then, after the mixture was cooled to room temperature, a mixture of the diastereoisomers of **3b** (50.0 mg, 0.12 mmol) and H_2O (0.09 mL, 4.8 mmol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at the same temperature. The solvent was then removed *in vacuo*, and the crude product was purified by silica gel flash chromatography with a 3:1 *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate eluent to give **5** as a single diastereoisomer as a yellow semisolid (26 mg, 59% yield): ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.89 (s, 1H), 7.80–7.79 (m, 2H), 7.58–7.54 (m, 1H), 7.44–7.39 (m, 4H), 7.04–7.02 (m, 2H), 4.38 (s, 1H), 3.91 (dt, $J = 8.5$ Hz, $J' = 4.2$ Hz, 1H), 3.15–3.05 (m, 2H), 2.30 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 199.2, 187.0, 161.2, 142.7, 138.5, 135.5, 133.6, 131.9 (2C), 129.2 (2C), 128.9 (2C), 128.9 (2C), 120.8, 53.2, 51.9, 42.2, 14.5; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3055, 2920, 1664, 1580, 1449, 1335, 1186 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrNaO}_2$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 391.0304, found 391.0303; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -159.6^\circ$ ($c = 1.20$ in CHCl_3); HPLC analysis ee 84% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 95:5 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 190$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 19.8$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 21.3$ min) at 25 °C.

One-Pot Preparation of Derivative 5. (4*R*,5*R*)-4-Benzoyl-5-(4-bromophenyl)-2-methylcyclopent-1-ene-1-carbaldehyde. To a screw cap septum vial containing EtOAc (2 mL) was added (S)-DPP-TMS **1** (0.048 mmol, 0.20 equiv), followed by the addition of *trans*-4-bromocinnamaldehyde **2b** (51 mg, 0.24 mmol, 1.0 equiv) and isoxazolone derivative **3a** (72 mg, 0.36 mmol, 1.5 equiv). Then, $\text{Pd}_2(\text{dba})_3$ (11 mg, 0.012 mmol, 0.05 equiv) was added. After full conversion was reached, the solvent was removed and to the crude reaction mixture in MeCN (2 mL) were added $\text{Mo}(\text{CO})_6$ (190 mg, 0.72 mmol, 3 equiv) and H_2O (0.17 mL, 9.6 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed using an oil bath for 3 h and then stirred at room temperature for an additional 17 h. Then, the solvent was removed *in vacuo*, and the crude product was purified by silica gel flash chromatography with a 3:1 *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate eluent to give **5** as one diastereoisomer as a yellow semisolid (36 mg, 41% yield): $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -170.6^\circ$ ($c = 1.15$ in CHCl_3); HPLC analysis ee 84% (Daicel Chiralpak IA column, 95:5 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, $\lambda = 190$ nm; retention times, $t_{\text{minor}} = 19.8$ min, $t_{\text{major}} = 21.3$ min) at 25 °C.

Preparation of Derivative 6. (4*R*,5*R*)-4-Benzoyl-5-(4-bromophenyl)-2-methylcyclopent-1-ene-1-carboxylic Acid. The title compound was prepared according to the procedure for the preparation of compound **4**. The crude product was purified by silica gel flash chromatography in a 20:1 DCM/MeOH eluent to give **6** as a yellow semisolid (38 mg, 73% yield): ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.79–7.77 (m, 2H), 7.57–7.53 (m, 1H), 7.44–7.38 (m, 4H), 7.03–7.00 (m, 2H), 4.42 (s, 1H), 3.82 (dt, $J = 8.8$ Hz, $J' = 4.6$ Hz, 1H), 3.06–2.95 (m, 1H), 2.23 (s, 3H); $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (151 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 199.3, 169.8, 158.5, 143.4, 135.7, 133.5, 131.9 (2C), 129.2 (2C), 128.9 (2C), 128.8 (2C), 128.3, 120.7, 54.8, 52.0, 42.7, 16.7; FT-IR (KBr) ν 3058, 3019, 2642, 1676, 1643, 1577, 1443, 1344, 1242 cm^{-1} ; HRMS (ESI) m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrNaO}_3$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 409.0238, found 409.0261; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = -161.0^\circ$ ($c = 1.00$ in CHCl_3);

HPLC analysis ee 84% (Daicel Chiralpak IG column, 70:30 heptane/*iso*-propanol, 1.0 mL/min, λ = 200 nm; retention times, t_{minor} = 13.2 min, t_{major} = 15.6 min) at 25 °C.

Scale-up Asymmetric Preparation of 3a. To a screw cap septum vial containing EtOAc (6 mL) was added catalyst (*S*)-DPP-TMS **1** (0.024 mmol, 0.20 equiv), followed by addition of (*E*)-cinnamaldehyde **2a** (132 mg, 1.0 mmol, 1.0 equiv) and isoxazolone derivative **1a** (318 mg, 1.5 mmol, 1.5 equiv). Then, Pd₂(dba)₃ (46 mg, 0.05 mmol, 0.05 equiv) was added. After full conversion was reached (TLC monitoring), the solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the crude reaction mixture (dr 2:1) was purified through silica gel flash chromatography (*n*-Hex/EtOAc), affording the desired spirocyclic compound as two separable diastereoisomers: **3a-major**: 149 mg, 45% yield, 86% ee. **3a-minor**: 89 mg, 27% yield, 99% ee.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Data Availability Statement

The data underlying this study are available in the published article and its [Supporting Information](#).

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.joc.4c02921>.

X-ray data for compounds **3e-major**, **3h-major**, **3r-major**, and **6** and chiral HPLC chromatograms of **3a–t** and **4–6** (PDF)

FAIR data, including the primary NMR FID files, for compounds **1a–c**, **2b–n**, **3a–t**, and **4–6** (ZIP)

Accession Codes

Deposition Numbers [2363082–2363085](#) contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via the joint Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC) and Fachinformationszentrum Karlsruhe [Access Structures](#) service.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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